

METHODS OF ITS TEACHING IN THE SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL LITERATURE

Zilola Ergasheva Sadullaevna

Senior teacher of the Chair "World languages and literature" The Uzbek State Institute of Arts and Culture

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7434200>

Abstract. This article provides information about the role of words in our language and their use in many senses, as well as the types of use, the most common methods of semantic transfer in our speech. In addition, the works of our great linguists provide theoretical information and their views on the transfer of meaning, as well as on the means of increasing the attractiveness and effectiveness of speech in the formation of written speech.

Keywords: metaphor, metonymy, synecdoche, polysemy, semantics, speech, linguistics, similarity, art, sensitivity, content.

МЕТОДИКА ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ИТС В НАУЧНО-МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ЛИТЕРАТУРЕ

Аннотация. В данной статье представлена информация о роли слов в нашем языке и их употреблении во многих смыслах, а также о видах употребления, наиболее распространенных способах смысловой передачи в нашей речи. Кроме того, в трудах наших великих языковедов представлены теоретические сведения и их взгляды на передачу смысла, а также на средства повышения привлекательности и эффективности речи при формировании письменной речи.

Ключевые слова: метафора, метонимия, синекдоха, полисемия, семантика, речь, лингвистика, сходство, искусство, импрессионизм, осмысленность.

A very large part of the words in our language are ambiguous, because if people use separate words for each of the newly emerging concepts in their daily lives, the number of words will be too much. would be multiplied and it would be impossible to store them in memory. As a result, the language became more difficult to use, and it gradually became obsolete. That is why in every language an attempt is made to express infinite concepts and ideas from different combinations of numerical language units. As a result, new meanings are added to words that already exist in the language. As a result, many meaningful words emerge. For example, the word "stone" was originally used to mean a hard, cold body: "A stone is lying on the road." began to be used in the sense of chma. Or if the word "eye" was originally used only to mean a convex organ of vision of a living organism, then "tree eye", based on the activation of the meaning of the bubble, light began to be used in the sense of 'window eye' by activating the meaning of 'providing'. Words used in speech with two or more meanings are called polysemous words or polysemy. Polysemy is derived from the Greek words poly - plural, semia - meaning plural. Polysemy is the opposite of monosemia (Greek mono bir, semia meaning).

No matter how many meanings there are in a polysemous word, it is still a single word. Therefore, in polysemous words, one of the meanings has a literal meaning (or its own meaning) and the rest have a figurative meaning. Figurative meanings appear in the context of speech when they are combined with other words, and when separated from the content of speech, the correct meaning remains the primary meaning. For example, the word stone means a solid body when separated from the speech environment. Synonymous words are rare in our language and

include scientific, professional terms, as well as emerging words. New words (neologisms) also have additional meanings over time. Knowing the meaning of polysemous words and using them appropriately in the speech process helps to make the speech effective and expressive. Exploring the ambiguity of a word is important, first and foremost, for lexical style. This is because it requires attention to the stylistic meaning of the word in its use in oral and written speech in order to have different meanings. Moving meaning from this beginning also creates humor, laughter, and various word games, such as synonymy, homonymy, and other lexical devices. At such times, the literal and figurative meanings of the word collide, resulting in an unexpected new meaning. These subtle nuances of words are widely used in fiction as an important visual medium. Movements are a common occurrence for oral speech. They cannot be used violently and can distort speech. They should only be approached by a writer or speaker if necessary. Otherwise, instead of increasing the value of the work of art, they can have a negative impact.

In the education system, according to the basis on which the transfer of meaning occurs in the lessons of the native language: 1. Metaphor 2. Metonymy 3. Synecdoche 4. Tasks such as functionality are studied. The most common way of conveying meaning in our speech is metaphor. Metaphor (Greek *metaphora* - transfer) is the transfer of the name of one object to another object on the basis of a certain similarity between them. For example, in the mouth of the tandoor, the meaning of the word mouth is based on its external resemblance to the mouth of a human or animal. The similarity between an object and an event can be on different grounds: 1. The formal similarity between two objects. For example, the human ear and the cauldron ear. 2. Similarity in the location of two objects. For example, a dog's tail, a plane's tail, and so on. Appropriate use of metaphors in speech makes our speech effective and engaging. Demonstrates the artistic and aesthetic ability of the speaker. Metonymy is derived from the Greek word —metonymy, which means to give another name. Metaphony, which is one of the main types of metaphorical meaning, is also based on the metaphorical meaning of words.

When metaphors copy objects and their signs that are similar to each other, metonymy compares the signs of objects that are completely different from each other, even if the two objects have some connection with their appearance or internal features. For example, Rana writes a letter to Anwar and says that you will read the rest of the story from Fuzuli. (A. Qadiri. Scorpion from the altar). In this case, the author's name is used instead of his work. Or, “After class, we went to my friend’s house to get A. Qadiri, and we can see that the work was used under the author’s name. In metonymy, the features of objects that are generally different from each other are compared, even if the two objects have some connection with each other in appearance or internal properties. Metonymy is a complex phenomenon of meaning transfer that attracts the attention of both linguists and literary critics at the same time.

While linguists approach this semantic shift from the point of view of discovering the characteristic features of semantics and semantics in polysemous words, from the point of view of the analysis of phenomena that form a semantic meaning, literary critics similarity, adjective, figurative allegory). The goal in both directions is the same, and that is to study the ambiguity of the word and its methodological possibilities. In metonymy in general, the meaning of an object within something is transferred to that thing. For example: I drank a bowl. I put down a plate, and the bowl means tea, and the plate means —osh. Or the author's name can be used in the work: I read Navoi, I read Oybek; again the result of the action is replaced by the name of the weapon that performed that action. For example: All these words belong to the pen of teacher S.

Ayni. Or again: Alisher, a lion with a chain that shakes the palace of poetry for five centuries, took the place where Temur's knife did not reach with a pen. One thing can be replaced with the material from which it is made

The word synecdoche is derived from the Greek word *dsynecdoche*, which means a whole through a part, and a part through a whole. At the heart of the synecdoche method is also the connection between objects. It can therefore be regarded as a form of metonymy, but in this connection the whole part relation is always evident. Let's look at some examples: The whole is represented by a part in the form of hoof-feeding (cattle or sheep-feeding), nail-biting (child-feeding). The words Uzbekistan won and Fergana came mean one person or group. In such cases, the part is represented by the whole. The essence of the method of functional transfer is that the meaning is transferred on the basis of functional similarity between the two objects. For example, the foot is an anatomical organ that serves to keep a person upright. This is what we call the leg of the chair. The human eye is the window eye (both to see), the bird's wing is the wing of the plane (both to fly).

The use of words in figurative senses to reveal the essence of the reality being described, that is, the use of words in figurative senses, has been studied scientifically, and the methods of teaching it have been specially studied methodologically. Regarding metaphor, B. Rakhmonova says: The main phenomenon that led to the ambiguity of lexemes in the language of fiction is metaphor. Metaphor as one of the most common ways to create figurative meaning is one of the most important elements of artistic speech, the art of speech. The formation of a figurative meaning in speech based on the semantics of the semantics is characteristic of almost all words that do not have this nature. Even auxiliary words can change the semantics of a task and create figurative meanings.

The phenomenon of metonymy has been studied by many scholars and various classifications have been given. For example, the scientist E. Kilichev in his book "Lexical means of artistic image" described metonymy as follows: "Metonymy is a form of polysemy. Words denoting an object or event have a new metaphorical meaning, in which objects and events that are radically different from each other and represent completely different concepts interact internally and externally in space and time. proximity, connection, connection. That is, the name of one object or event is transferred from one to another on the basis of constant interrelationships in space or time. "

Also, in this play, metonymy is based on comparison, only in metaphor the signs of similar objects are compared, while in metonymy these two objects have some connection with their appearance or internal features, but, in general, differ from each other. there are also opinions that the signs of (dissimilar) objects are compared. Metonymy is the most widely used artistic tool in fiction. Scholars U. Tursunov, J. Mukhtorov in their textbook "Modern Uzbek literary language" Rakhmonova B, Fayzieva D, Jabborkulova A. "The role of metaphor in the prose text. Current issues of Uzbek linguistics." - T. 2009. p. 67. Mirzayev M., Usmanov S., Rasulov I. Uzbek language. - T. Teacher, 1970. p. 45 p. Metonymy is divided into several types.

In synecdoche, meaning is transferred based on the part and the whole relationship. It is a form of metonymy. According to Mirtojiev, the phenomenon of polysemy in language has long attracted the attention of scientists. It was studied from the point of view of philosophy and methodology before the Common Era. According to our linguists, this issue was studied by Chinese and Indian scientists, and in the beginning of the present century by the Greeks. The

diversity of words has also been studied in works on the richness of the ancient Turkic language. Such a phenomenon can be observed in Mahmud Qashqari's *Devoni lug'otit turk* and Alisher Navoi's *Muhabbat-ul lug'tayn*. The variety of meanings of words is determined by the analysis of literary texts. The use of the word in a sense other than its own has been referred to in linguistics and literature as the term *trop*. R. Kungurov explains such a phenomenon in the language of art as follows: it's called. "

There are several views in world linguistics on the classification of words that form figurative meanings. For example, the French linguist J. Maruzo divides figurative words into three types: metaphor, metonymy, and synecdoche. The Russian linguist L. A. Bukhalovsky, on the other hand, divided the phenomenon of figurative meaning into six types: metaphor, function, emotionality, metonymy, as a folk etymology, and connection. L. A. Bukhalovsky considers synecdoche as a form of metonymy. Effectiveness of speech is one of the most important qualities of speech culture and is manifested in both oral and written forms of speech.

Although today in the methodology of teaching the native language to some extent studied issues related to the development of students' oral speech, the formation of speech culture, in the educational process, teachers students face a number of challenges in developing a culture of written speech, the formation in the reader of qualities such as accuracy, coherence, responsiveness of speech. Given the importance of the use of semantic transitions in the formation of oral and written speech, L. S. Vygotsky argues that "there is a great difference between oral and written speech." Because, firstly, written speech is more abstract than oral speech, and secondly, as a result of a change in the usual motivation in oral speech, i.e. the absence of intonation and the interlocutor, the reader focuses on written speech rather than the speech itself. rather, it will have to focus on the hidden meaning behind the words. Therefore, enriching written speech with impact and content can cause a number of problems for students.

The student will not only need to know the theoretical information about the means of enhancing the attractiveness and effectiveness of the speech, but also to think about how to include it in the text. In the textbook "Methods of teaching the native language" the study of the types of semantic migration, along with the development of speech culture, also affects the richness of the student's speech. It is manifested in the use of words and figurative meanings, the use of artistic language tools such as simile, adjective, animation, allegory, rhetoric, rhetorical interrogative sentences. These visual aids of language add beauty, charm and variety to speech. ” The textbook "Methods of teaching the Uzbek language", created under the leadership of B. Tokhliyev, contains a number of tasks related to the teaching of semantic transfer, in which the "Explanatory course" In the study - the spiritual relationship between self and figurative words, the study of semantic groups (such as synonyms, synonyms, antonyms) in the figurative sense. We find that working on the dictionary allows you to increase and enrich the vocabulary by learning the language levels.

T. Yusupova's article "Teaching lexicology using innovative technologies" also provides a number of methods and recommendations for the organization of teaching the methodological features of metaphor and metonymy on the basis of modern pedagogical technologies. M. Umurzakova's article "Teaching Metaphor and its Methodological Features" suggests the use of several methods in teaching the types of semantics in relation to other disciplines, ie integration. In this article, the author emphasizes the importance of private-author metaphors more than

traditional metaphors in the development of art, and emphasizes the need to inform students about migrations based on animal names, plant names. .

From the above, it is clear that the ways of meaning transfer have been sufficiently studied scientifically by world and Uzbek linguists. Based on this theoretical knowledge, as well as the main purpose of teaching the Uzbek language, to explain to students the importance of types of semantics in speech, the use of semantic types in students' speech. The development of a number of innovative methods related to this topic and their implementation in practice is one of the issues that need to be addressed in the field of Uzbek language teaching methodology.

REFERENCES

1. Tursunov U, Mukhtorov J. Rahmatullayev Sh. Modern Uzbek literary language textbook. - Tashkent. 1965. 125-b.
2. Mirtojiev M. "Polysemy in the Uzbek language". - Tashkent. Fan. 69-b.
3. Kungurov R. Visual aids of the Uzbek language. Tashkent. Fan, 1977. 54-p.
4. Maruzo J. Dictionary of linguistic terms. - M.: URSS, 2004.
5. Buxalovskiy L. A. Introduction to writing. M.: Uchpedgiz, 1954. - p.
6. Vygotskiy L. S. Myshlenie and rech. M., 2007. - p. 98.
7. Gulomov A., Kadyrov M. Methods of teaching the native language. - Tashkent. Science and Technology, 2012. 87 p.
8. Tokhliyev B., Shamsiyeva M., Ziyodova T. Methods of teaching the Uzbek language. - Tashkent. National Library of Uzbekistan. 2010. 45-p
9. Yusupova Tashkent. "Teaching lexicology using innovative technologies" Topical issues of Uzbek language teaching methods. Tashkent State University of Uzbek Language and Literature named after Alisher Navoi. - Tashkent. 2017. 74-b
10. Umurzokova M., Khojamberdiyeva Sh. "Teaching metaphor and its methodological features" Uzbekistan: Language and culture. III series. Uzbek language education. – Tashkent, 2017. 98-p.